

Morphological evaluation of karatekas (Kata and Kumite) of Algerian national teams

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Abstract

Karate is a sport requiring strength-speed, as each strike is an explosive impulse of short duration, followed by an impact requiring maximum force. Also, karate requires flexibility in the joints of the legs and hips when executing movements. For our work, we measured 17 karatekas, members of the national team, 09 practicing kumite with a height of $174.08 \text{ cm} \pm 15.7$; a weight of $74.61 \text{ kg} \pm 6.65$ and a sporting seniority of $14.11 \text{ years} \pm 1.83$. Kata practitioners have a height of $171.38 \text{ cm} \pm 4.6$; a weight of $67.33 \text{ kg} \pm 4.95$ and a sporting seniority of $13 \text{ years} \pm 2.6$. The anthropometric method was used for all the measurements from which we calculated the different indices of physical development as well as the components of body weight. We have found that kumite practitioners present higher indices than those of kata. We therefore conclude that the morphological parameters of the two styles of practice are different and that they must be taken into consideration when orienting towards the style of karate to practice.

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Introduction:

Morphological indices are of great importance in assessing the state of the human body. In the preparation of athletes, morphological data is used to check the effectiveness of the influence of training on the organism when dealing with the problems of sports orientation and selection. Anthropological research data is more applied in practice. We are currently using analysis of total and partial parameters (height/weight), analysis of the components of body mass, analysis of the correlation between the mass of body segments, the topography of muscular strength and joint mobility. What about studies of morphotypology in combat sports in general and karate in particular?

Karate is undoubtedly one of the most widely practiced sports in the world. Traditional karate training involves basic techniques, katas and combat activities (Imamura, 1998). Modern karate tournaments consist of two equally important karate disciplines: kumite and kata. In the past, the requirements of karate competitions were similar for both disciplines, as well as for standard training programs. When we look at the question of optimizing performance, several models are proposed in an attempt to understand it better, whether it be the bio-informational approach (cognitivist model, neurophysiology), biomechanics (Hay, 1980; Goubel 1998, Van Hocke, 1980) or psychology and bioenergy (Astrand 1993, Fox, Mathews 1993). Considering the components of karate performance will be decisive mainly for the analysis of the constraints of the activity and the analysis of the athletes' resources.

Karate, with its two events - kata and kumite - requires several physical components: speed, strength, power, endurance, flexibility and morphology: weight, height, body fat percentage and muscle mass. Competitive karate has two facets: kumite (combat) and kata (demonstration of conventional forms). The very high level achieved in all sporting disciplines has prompted sports researchers to investigate all aspects of sporting performance. When training has enabled a very high level of performance to be achieved, the most appropriate morphology will be a decisive factor in winning (Schurch P. 1984).

Sport morphology is based on the physical development of everyone, i.e. all the physical parameters relating to good work capacity. These parameters are represented by height, weight, body surface area, body mass, i.e. fat, muscle and bone mass; physical constitution and morphological parameters:

indexes of strength, flexibility, etc. (Touabti-Mimouni N, 2015). Current scientific research in the field of sport has confirmed the importance of morpho-functional and physical data in the careers of top-level athletes. Carter et al (2009) state that the experimental data obtained when measuring the anthropometric indexes of the best athletes confirms the need to have a particular morphotype to succeed in the corresponding speciality.

In Algeria, there are few studies dealing with the morphology of the karateka. For example, we cite the magisterial work of Mokrani B. (2001) dealing with the morphological profiles of karatekas in general. A comparative analysis of the types of practice (kumite and kata) was not addressed. This led us to reflect on the morphological characteristics of karatekas practicing kumite and kata and to see if there was a difference in their typology. As a result, participants were often used to competing successfully in both kata and kumite. However, the alternation of competition rules has made kumite competitions both more dynamic and more attractive (Macan, 2006). Kata competition has evolved a great deal since its requirements have changed considerably compared to kumite: physical, technical, tactical, physiological, morphological and psychological. As a result, it has become more important for elite karate competitors to specialize in kata and kumite because their requirements are totally different. Kumite is a combat that consists of a confrontation between two practitioners. This confrontation is based on an exchange of kicks and punches, possibly with the use of projections and/or sweeps. It can also be said to be a controlled percussion duel in which karatekas must score points using techniques executed with the help of their hands.

A kata is a series of formalized, codified movements performed without an opponent, following a set pattern. It is the codified transposition of a fight against imaginary opponents. The starting point is followed by a series of attack and defense techniques in response to the supposed movements of the opponents. The remarkable level of sporting results achieved is the result of a better understanding and mastery of all the factors whose interaction determines performance. These factors are physiological, morphological and psychological.

Even if we can speak of an ideal morphotype for combat sports practitioners, because there are some excellent fighters who escape classification, we can nevertheless identify, when comparing fighters of the same weight, several

particularities which can be assets for the sport in question. The ‘seated height/standing height’ ratio, which measures the length of the lower limbs, is a particularly high morphological index among world-class karate practitioners (Tisal H. 1999). The greater the height between the legs, the greater the length of the lower limb. The karatekas in the national teams all have a long body type. Given that in karate, points can be scored with both the upper and lower limbs, top-level karatekas should have significant lengths for both these parameters. The musculature of the lower limbs is another interesting factor to consider. The ideal karateka will have a powerful thigh and a thin calf (Tisal H. 1999).

In addition to the tactical, physiological and psychological aspects, the morphological aspect plays a determining role in performance and high level. Several studies have been carried out on the profile of karatekas, including Giampietro M, Pujia A, Bertini I., (2003); they showed the somatotype of elite athletes and amateur athletes; elite athletes show a mesomorphic ectomorphic somatotype; they are characterized by a slightly forward longitudinal development of the skeletal framework, whereas amateur athletes show a balanced mesomorphic type and also these two groups of athletes Many sports specialists have very strict requirements with regard to the morphology of athletes. This is assessed according to two criteria: total measurements and physical proportion (Mimouni N 1996). The morphology of a karateka will condition the scope of his technique; a practitioner of average height and strong build will benefit from a relative lengthening of his limbs and will be better at defense than at attack; and a taller and slimmer karateka will attack his opponent with whipped and very fast techniques. Paradoxically, a tall karateka may be able to deliver very powerful blows, but his mobility and offensive techniques are much slower.

2. Methodology:

J.E. Lindsay Carter J.E.L and, Timothy R. Ackland T.R. (2009), attest that anthropometric data are of capital importance, because in certain disciplines performances depend on the particularities of the body constitution; this is why our curiosity requires us to take an interest in the morphological side in order to :

- evaluate the morphological parameters and indices of Algerian karatekas practicing kumite and kata. Our study was therefore carried out on senior

male karatekas competing at national and international level. All these athletes are karate specialists (kata and kumite).

Table 1: Total parameters

Subjects	Average (\pm SD)	
	Kumite group (n= 09)	Kata group (n=08)
Height (cm)	174,08 \pm 15,71	171,38 \pm 4,6
Weight (kg)	74,61 \pm 6,65	67,33 \pm 4,95
Expérience (année)	14,11 \pm 1,83	13,00 \pm 2,56

We assume that knowledge of athlete typology would enable the coach to better understand the training process. Control of morphotypology would enable better management of training according to fighting style (kumite or kata). The main objective of our research is to determine the morphotypology of practicing karatekas (kata, kumite).

2. 1 Characteristics of the sample

The sample chosen for our research work consists of a group of 17 adult karatekas aged between 17 and 27. They are all members of the Algerian national teams preparing for the Mediterranean Games (June 2022) and the World Championships (2022).

The measurements were taken during the day (morning) at a temperature of around 22 degrees, using basic anthropometric techniques. These athletes have been training regularly for over 10 years.

The main instruments used in our research are as follows:

- An anthropometric kit of the G.P.M. (Siber Hegner) type containing: The MARTIN system anthropometer, designed to measure the linear (longitudinal) and transverse dimensions of the body, the thickness compass with olive tips: for small diameters, the tape measure for measuring the perimeters of the body and its segments. A LANGE-type folding forceps (Cambridge Scientific Industries, Cambridge, Maryland) for measuring adipose panicles to an accuracy of 10g/mm² and a medical scale for weight measurement.

From the various measurements we calculated the physical development indices for each athlete.

2.2. Physical development indices

- Calculation of body surface area

Body surface area, expressed in m², is the main indicator of an athlete's state of physical development. The greater the surface area, the better the athlete's physical development. Body surface area is calculated using the formula of (Izakson, 1956), which considers both weight and height.

$$S (m^2) = 1 + \{P + (T-160)/100\}$$

S: Body surface area in square meters (m²)

T: Height in centimeters (cm)

P: Weight in kilograms (kg)

- Index by E. Schreider (1953):

Expressed in kg/m², this index gives us information about an individual's level of robustness. The formula for calculating this index is as follows:

$$IR = P/Sa, \text{ kg/m}^2.$$

IR: robustness index expressed in kg/m².

P: body weight in kg

Sa: absolute body surface area in m².

- Energy expenditure index

According to (Mimouni, 2015), this index provides us with information on the degree of energy expenditure by an athlete as a function of body surface area and weight, through more economical use and limiting the loss of energy reserves. The lower the value of this index, the better the energy saving, which leads to greater resistance to work intensity. This index is calculated as follows

$$SP = Sa/P \text{ cm}^2/\text{kg}$$

SP: energy expenditure index expressed in cm²/kg

Sa: absolute body surface area in m².

P: body weight in kg

- **Quetelet index:** This index reveals an individual's level of physical development. It is expressed in g/cm, according to Quetelet's formula (1869), the value of which is 350 for sedentary people and over 400 g/cm for top-level athletes (Mimouni, 1996).

Its formula is as follows: $IQ = P/T \text{ g/cm}$

IQ: Quetelet index in g/cm

P: body weight in kg T: height in centimetres

- Kaup index (1921) or BMI (body mass index):

Otherwise known as Davenport's Body Build Index (1921), it divides body weight by the square of height and is expressed in grams per square centimetre:

$$IK = P/T^2 \text{ g/cm}^2$$

To interpret the results of this index, we use the following scale, developed by DAVENPORT and quoted by Vandervael, (1980).

Table 2: Evaluation of the Kaup index

Interpretation	Values
Very skinny	1,40 à 1,80
Lean	1,81 à 2,14
Medium	2,15 à 2,56
Corpulent	2,57 à 3,05
Obese	3,06 et plus

- Sheldon index

This index tells us about the length of an individual. It is calculated according to the following formula:

$$ISh = T^3 \sqrt{P}$$

SH: Sheldon index expressed in cm/gr.

T: size in centimeter.

P: body weight in kg.

2.3 Body weight composition

Body weight is one of the most important indicators of physical development. The components of body weight are: fat, bone and muscle mass. The components of body weight are determined by the anthropometric method which does not require very sophisticated equipment and is easy to use.

The components of body weight are calculated according to the following formulas:

▪ Fatty component

In order to determine the fatty component, in our research work, we use the formula of the Czech researcher (Mateigka, 1921) which takes into consideration the seven skin folds:

$$M.G = d \times S \times k$$

M.G: quantity of general fat in the skin (kg)

K: constant = 1.3

S: body surface

▪ Muscular component:

The following formula allows us to define the absolute quantity of the muscle component in body weight:

$$M.M = L \times R^2 \times K$$

M: represents the absolute quantity of muscle tissue (kg)

L: this is the length of the body in centimeters

R: average size of the radii of the arm, forearm, thigh and leg in the regions where the volume of the muscles is most developed, not counting the skin layer

K: a constant which is equal to 6.5

▪ Bone component

Expressed in kilogram (kg) according to the following formula which determines the absolute quantity of the bone component.

$$M.O \text{ (kg)} = T \times O2 \times K$$

M.O: the absolute mass of bone tissue.

T: height of the individual in cm

O2: square of the average size of the distal parts of the arm, forearm, thigh, leg
K: constant equal to 1.2

To carry out all the calculations, we used the Windows Excel 2010 software and the software (STATISTICA, 2011).

3. Results:

3.1. Analysis of the total parameters of kata and kumite karatekas:

Table no. 3: Representation of the total parameters of kata karatekas

	Practise (Years)	Weight (Kg)	Height (cm)
Kata	13,00±2,56	67,33±4,95	171,38±4,60
Kumite	14,11±1,83	74,61±6,65	174,08±15,71
CV% Kata	19,72	7,35	2,68
CV% Kumité	12,99	8,91	9,02

The average value of the weight of kata karatekas is 67.33±4.95kg, a coefficient of variation of 7.35%, which shows that the group is very homogeneous while kumite practitioners have an average weight of 74.61±6.65kg, the coefficient of variation expressed great homogeneity with a value of 8.91%.

The vertex expressing the height of the kata practitioners is 171.38±4.60cm, with a coefficient of variation showing great homogeneity of the group. Kumite practitioners have an average height of 174.08±15.71cm) the coefficient of variation is 9.02%, presenting great homogeneity.

For karateka practicing kumite, the average sporting seniority is 14.11±1.83 years, the coefficient of variation with a value of 12.99%. Regarding seniority for kata practitioners, the average is 13.00±2.56 years with a coefficient of variation of 19.72%. The two groups present average homogeneity.

3.2 The longitudinal dimensions of kata and kumite karatekas:

Figure 1 : Longitudinal dimensions of karateka

The average value of the upper limb length of kata karatekas is 77.41 ± 4.09 cm, a coefficient of variation of 5.28% while kumite practitioners have a length of 81.20 ± 3.24 cm, with a coefficient of variation of 3.98% which shows us significant homogeneity for the two groups at the level of this segment.

The average length of the lower limb of kata karatekas is 93.55 ± 4.26 cm, with a coefficient of variation of 4.55% and that of kumite practitioners an average value of 97.82 ± 4.33 cm, with a coefficient of variation of 4.43%. The two groups show great homogeneity. For all other lengths, the two groups are homogeneous.

Regardless of size (Jaric, 2005), kumite competitors should benefit from greater longitudinal body dimensions allowing them to reach and strike an opponent sooner, particularly during interceptions. However, a typical kata competition involves a number of traditional karate postures that are rather weak and therefore quite strength demanding. Since muscle strength increases with body size at a rate lower than body weight (Jaric, 2005), kata competitors could benefit from a smaller body size.

3.3 The transverse dimensions of kata and kumite karatekas:

3.3.1: Diameters of the upper part of the body of kata and kumite karatekas

Table no. 4: Representation of the diameters of the upper part of the body of kata and kumite karatekas

	DT (cm)	DBIAC (cm)	DTRTH (cm)	DAPTH (cm)	DDB (cm)	DDAB (cm)
Kata	$13,46 \pm 1,19$	$33,91 \pm 2,36$	$27,81 \pm 1,11$	$19,51 \pm 0,71$	$7,00 \pm 1,01$	$5,36 \pm 0,64$
Kumité	$13,50 \pm 1,26$	$34,69 \pm 1,83$	$28,64 \pm 2,19$	$20,88 \pm 1,15$	$7,71 \pm 1,34$	$5,50 \pm 0,77$

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CV% Kata	8,87	6,96	3,97	3,62	14,49	11,96
CV% Kumité	9,36	5,27	7,63	5,51	17,42	14,00

The biacromial diameter of the kata is equal to 33.91 ± 2.36 cm, with a coefficient of variation of 6.96%, for the kumite it is equal to 34.69 ± 1.83 cm, with a coefficient of variation of 5.27%, which means that there is great homogeneity for the two groups.

Concerning the transverse diameter of the thorax, we note that the average is 27.81 ± 1.11 cm, with a coefficient of variation of 3.97% for the kata and an average is 28.64 ± 2.19 cm, with a coefficient variation of 7.63% for kumite, presenting great homogeneity.

The distal arm diameter of our kata population records an average of 7.00 ± 1.01 cm, with a coefficient of variation of 14.49% while the kumite practitioners the average is 7.71 ± 1.34 cm, with a coefficient of variation of (17.42%) which presents average homogeneity.

3.3.2 The diameters of the lower part of the body of karatekas:

Figure n°2: The diameters of the lower part of the body of karatekas (DBIC: bicretal diameter, DBITR: bitrochanteric diameter, DDC: distal thigh diameter, DDJ: distal leg diameter).

The average bicretal distal of kata practitioners is 25.58 ± 3.32 cm, with an average homogeneity or the coefficient of variation is 13.00%. The average bicretal distal of the kumite is 26.00 ± 2.20 cm, with great homogeneity or the coefficient of variation is 8.45%.

For kata, the bitrochanteric diameter is 30.25 ± 3.23 cm, with a coefficient of variation of 10.68%, with average homogeneity and for kumite, the average is 31.72 ± 1.45 cm, with a coefficient of variation of 4.56%, so there is great homogeneity.

The average of the distal thigh diameter of kata practitioners is 9.33 ± 0.53 cm, with a coefficient of variation of 3.70% and for kumite, the value is 9.82 ± 0.54 cm, with a coefficient variation of 5.50%. The two groups show great homogeneity.

For the distal diameter of the leg, the average for the kata is 7.04 ± 0.51 cm (CV% 7.20) with a coefficient of variation expressing great homogeneity. It is the same for kumite where the average is 6.87 ± 0.38 cm (CV%: 5.50).

3.4 Circumferences of Kata and kumite karatekas:

Figure 3 : Circumferences of Kata and kumite karatekas:

Despite some high values among kumite practitioners, the athletes present great homogeneity for all the parameters measured. The same goes for kumite practitioners.

3.5 The skin folds of kata and kumite karatekas

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Figure 4: Skin folds of karateka (kata and kumite).

Whatever the site measured, we note a very great heterogeneity of the skin folds. This therefore pushes us to be more interested in the fat mass among karatekas of these styles.

3.6 Indices of physical development of kata karatekas

Table no. 5: Representation of physical development indices for kata karatekas

	Surface	Schreider	IDE	Quetelet	Kaup	Livi	Sheldon
Kumite	1,89±0,16	39,76±4,69	254,43±28,38	432,94±64,98	2,54±0,65	1,30±0,19	7,06±1,02
Kata	1,79±0,08	37,65±1,45	265,96±10,04	392,74±24,89	2,29±0,15	1,18±0,07	7,66±0,47
CV% K	0,08	1,45	10,04	24,89	0,15	0,07	0,47
CV% K	4,68	3,84	3,78	6,34	6,43	6,34	6,14

- ✓ } For the values obtained by Kata practitioners, we notice great homogeneity in the group.
- ✓ } For kumite practitioners, the indices present average homogeneity for all the calculated indices.

3.7 The components of the body weight of kata karatekas

Table no. 6: Representation of the body weight components of kata karatekas

	MA	MA%	MO	MO%	MM	MM%
Kata	7,69±3,28	11,47±4,94	10,63±1,02	15,80±1,23	35,29±3,70	52,42±3,93
Kumite	7,33±3,49	9,98±5,14	11,73±2,03	15,77±2,57	38,14±5,91	51,02±5,28
CV% Kumite	47,61	51,48	17,32	16,31	15,49	10,34
CV% Kata	42,69	43,10	9,60	7,79	10,48	7,50

Figure 5: Representation of the body composition of Kata and Kumite karatekas

The average value of the fat mass of kata karatekas is 7.69 ± 3.28 kg, a coefficient of variation of 42.69%. The average value of the fat mass of kumite karatekas is 9.98 ± 5.14 kg, a coefficient of variation of 51.48%. The two groups exhibit significant heterogeneity. The bone mass in kata practitioners is 10.63 ± 1.02 kg, compared to kumite where the values are 15.77 ± 2.57 kg with a coefficient of variation of 16.31%. Homogeneity is average. The muscle mass recorded in kata is 35.29 ± 3.70 kg (CV%: 10.48%), and for kumite the value is 51.02 ± 5.28 kg (CV%: 10.34%, this which presents average homogeneity in the two groups.

Discussion:

Body shape can have a significant impact on performance during karate exams. However, regular practice, technique and understanding of the principles of karate remain essential for success (Chaabène et al. 2015). Each individual can exploit their morphological advantages and work on their weaknesses to progress in this martial art (Iidle et al. (2008). To follow up on our results, the statistical treatment of the morphological parameters allowed us to draw up a diagnosis which will allow us to make it possible to propose corrective measures concerning the strategy pursued by the coaches regarding the planning and implementation of the various programs to prepare karatekas for international competition. The anthropometric variables recorded from the karatekas tested were comparable. to those of elite karate athletes tested in previous studies (Ravier, 2004; Nêma et al., 2003; Fritzsche, 2007).

Indexes of physical development: Age, weight and stature have always been determining factors in achieving performance as stated (Thomas, 1981). These two characteristics allowed us to calculate a series of indices relating to the body constitution of karatekas. The body surface area index is linked to weight and height. Thus, the greater the values of its indices, the more the surface area of the body increases. However, Karate is characterized by a weight category system. This index provides us with information on the state of physical development. Izakson (1956) believes that the greater this index, the better the physical development. The Kaup index or body build index (Body Mass Index) characterizes the level of physical development. The interpretation of the results is based on a scale developed by Davenport cited by (Vandervael, 1980). For the Quetelet index we find high results among the namely that the values of our two groups express a very high physical development. You should also know that this index is also proportional to weight and height. (Claessens et al., 1987) indicates that the high-level athlete is characterized by a robust constitution, with developed diameters and circumferences and a small development of subcutaneous fat.

Body composition is an essential factor in karate performance, as it directly influences key aspects such as power, agility, speed and endurance (Sterkovicz S., Francini E. (2009).

Body composition includes several elements: good muscle mass promotes punching power, stability and resistance. A low body fat percentage

improves speed, agility and reduces fatigue. And a strong bone structure is important for withstanding impacts and maintaining stable positions (Wilmore, 1983). Our karatekas have a significant body fat, which can harm performance. This parameter must be taken into consideration.

In kumite (combat), athletes favor a body composition focused on speed and agility, with a low percentage of fat and explosive musculature.

In Kata (forms) : Precision and stability are essential. The emphasis is on muscular coordination and flexibility. A study on elite karateka shows that athletes with a low-fat percentage (<12% for men, <20% for women) have better performances in kumite and kata. Strategies for controlling body weight and fat mass aim to promote performance by reducing the ratio between muscle mass and fat mass (Koutedakis et al., 1994). Appropriate monitoring seems necessary, depending on the specificities of the sport and the athlete.

Conclusion:

The relationship between karate and body shape is an interesting topic that explores how physical characteristics influence the abilities of practitioners. The different styles of karate (Kata, Kumite) promote distinct morphological qualities. Studies show that morpho typological assessment helps guide training: personalized planning, injury prevention, optimization of techniques. Our results show that our karatekas have anthropometric parameters specific to the fighting style.

Nowadays, in high-level sport, morpho functional qualities are decisive in obtaining high-level results. Good planning of training programs (short term and long term) must be done considering the morphological characteristics of each individual with a view to individualization during the athlete's training.

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